

MODEL KINERJA BERBASIS NILAI-NILAI BUDAYA ORGANISASI PADA PEGAWAI KANWIL KEMENTERIAN AGAMA PROVINSI BANTEN

Mohamad Duddy Dinantara¹, Hadyati Harras²
Universitas Pamulang, Banten
dosen00816@unpam.ac.id¹, dosen01046@unpam.ac.id²

Submitted: 26th July 2020/ **Edited:** 27th Sept 2020/ **Issued:** 01st October 2020
Cited on: Dinantara, M. D., & Harras, H. (2020). MODEL KINERJA BERBASIS
NILAI-NILAI BUDAYA ORGANISASI PADA PEGAWAI KANWIL
KEMENTERIAN AGAMA PROVINSI BANTEN. *SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL OF
REFLECTION: Economic, Accounting, Management and Business*, 3(4), 371-380.
DOI: 10.37481/sjr.v3i2.187
<https://doi.org/10.37481/sjr.v3i2.187>

ABSTRACT

Building public trust is the core of public services, but currently at the Regional Office of Banten Religion Ministry, public trust has not been built. The negative stigma of society, such as lack of transparency, many civil servants who act on behalf of religion take advantage of the public's ignorance on Hajj and Umrah management, and poor management of religious education. Therefore, this study was conducted seeing to what extent the employees of Banten Religion Ministry performed, and to analyze work culture factors had an impact on performance. This study uses quantitative methods, research sample is 67 respondents, sampling technique is simple random, research instrument uses a questionnaire, and the analysis method uses linear regression. The results showed that professional work culture contributed dominantly to performance. This finding confirms that the professional working model in the Banten Religion Ministry is more prominent than other cultural values.

Keywords: Integrity, Professionalism, Innovative, Responsibility, Exemplary, Performance

PENDAHULUAN

Tuntutan reformasi birokrasi menjadi isu hangat di lingkungan pemerintahan, tidak terkecuali di lembaga Kementerian Agama. Menghadirkan tata kelola pemerintahan yang bersih menjadi *tag line* utama, pasalnya tuntutan globalisasi telah memaksa seluruh lembaga untuk menghadirkan daya saing yang sarat akan efektivitas dan efisiensi (Wahyudi, 2018). Tuntutan tersebut, secara eksplisit menasar pada kualitas sumber daya manusia. Sebagaimana amanat UU Nomor 5 Tahun 2014 tentang Aparatur Sipil Negara pada pasal 3 juga memasukkan kinerja sebagai salah satu prinsip